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Research Article

**A RESEARCH TO ESTABLISH AN ASSOCIATION BETWEEN
LIPID PROFILE AND INCIDENCE OF DIABETES AMONG
GENERAL POPULATION OF PAKISTAN**¹Munazza Mehak, ¹Aqsa Ibrahim, ²Fakhra Hussain¹Fatima Jinnah Medical University Lahore²Muhammad Medical College Mir Pur Khas Sindh**Abstract:**

Background and Objectives: Pakistan faces the major issue of emerging Diabetes Mellitus (DM) among the general population with an affected population of seven million which will cross the figure fourteen million by 2040. This increase in the diabetic patients' places Pakistan among eight highly affected countries. These countries are under a diabetic burden with an increasing number of patients affected by diabetes. In this particular research, we aim to assess the levels of TG and lipid profile among diabetic patients and their interdependence.

Methodology: We completed this research in the timeframe of March 2017 to November 2017 at Fatima Jinnah Medical University Lahore on a total of one hundred patients who visited the OPD of the hospital. We documented the information about the one hundred patients of diabetes in the nine months during this research. The research sample consisted of both males and females. The patients were enrolled in the age bracket of (35 – 65) years. Clinical investigations included serum TC, fasting glucose plasma, serum TG, serum LDL-C and serum HDL-C calculated through Randox kit.

Results: We conclude that there is a significant and strong association of diabetic retinopathy severity with serum TC, fasting glucose plasma, serum TG, serum LDL-C and serum HDL-C; whereas, diabetes mellitus duration and age also showed a positive and moderate relation with diabetes severity.

Conclusion: As per the research outcomes we conclude that a significant and strong association of diabetic retinopathy severity with serum TC, fasting glucose plasma, serum TG, serum LDL-C and serum HDL-C. A strong positive association was also persistent among HbA1c and BSF with serum TC, serum TG, serum LDL-C; while, serum HDL-C had a negatively weak relation with HbA1c and BSF.

Keywords: Fasting, Diabetes, Lipids, Glucose, Serum and Cholesterol.

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INTRODUCTION:

Pakistan faces the major issue of emerging Diabetes Mellitus (DM) among the general population with an affected population of seven million which will cross the figure fourteen million by 2040 [1]. This increase in the diabetic patients' places Pakistan among eight highly affected countries. These countries are under a diabetic burden with an increasing number of patients affected by diabetes. The mortality and morbidity which is associated with diabetes mellitus are because of microvascular complications which include nephropathy, retinopathy and neuropathy. Their microvascular complications have an association with chronic hyperglycemia, increased species of reactive oxygen, increased fatty acids and reduced nitric oxides as they alter the vascular response [2]. Diabetic retinopathy is one of the major ocular complications as it leads to irreversible blindness. This irreversible blindness is newly typed II diabetes diagnosed retinopathy with a prevalence rate of forty percent [3]. Diabetic retinopathy's progression and development mostly rely on diabetes duration, gender, age, BMI, hypertension, glycemic control, nephropathy, pregnancy, smoking and levels of serum lipid [4].

A number of authors from all over the world have presented varying outcomes about the progression and development of diabetic retinopathy in multiple series. Diabetic dyslipidemia which is featured through TC, TG, LDL-C and HDL-C are among potential risk factors of diabetic retinopathy [5]. Hyperlipidemia attributes to an endothelial dysfunction because of the decreased nitric oxide bioavailability and blood-retinal barrier breakdown which leads to exudation of lipoproteins and serum lipids. The exudation of lipoproteins and serum lipids causes the alteration of diabetic retinopathy outcomes and the formation of DME (Diabetic Macular Edema) [6]. Therefore, in this particular research, we aim to assess the levels of TG and lipid profile among diabetic patients and their interdependence.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

We completed this research in the timeframe of March 2017 to November 2017 at Fatima Jinnah Medical University Lahore on a total of one hundred patients who visited the OPD of the hospital. We documented the information about the one hundred patients of diabetes in the nine months during this research. The research sample consisted of both males and females. The patients were enrolled in the age bracket of (35 – 65) years. Clinical investigations included serum TC, fasting glucose plasma, serum TG, serum LDL-C and serum HDL-C calculated through Randox kit. The researcher used SPSS software for statistical analysis of the research outcomes. Descriptive statistics which include Mean and SD values for quantitative values (diabetic retinopathy duration, age, body mass index, Lipid sub-fractional values, Blood Sugar Fasting & HbA1C) and the frequencies value with the percentage of the smoking and gender (qualitative variables) described the research outcomes. Research also analyzed quantitative data through Sample T-Test, Chi-Square Test, ANOVA and Post Hoc analysis (P-Value under 0.05).

RESULTS:

In the light of demographic values, it is evident that an association between hyperlipidemia and diabetes is persistent among the Pakistani population. HbA1C value is (5.77 ± 0.50) among the patients of diabetes than normal group patients. We conclude that there is a significant and strong association of diabetic retinopathy severity with serum TC, fasting glucose plasma, serum TG, serum LDL-C and serum HDL-C; whereas, diabetes mellitus duration and age also showed a positive and moderate relation with diabetes severity. Detailed outcomes about the male population, smokers, biochemical features, clinical features and lipid sub-fractional values are respectively given in Table – I, II and III.

Table – I: Male Population and Smoker's Stratification

Diseased Group (Variables)	Number	Percentage	P-Value
Male	71	50.71	0.285
Smoker	32	22.85	< 0.01

Table – II: Biochemical and Clinical Features

Diseased Group (Variables)	Mean	±SD	P-Value
Age (Years)	48.04	4.83	0.018
Duration (Years)	4.60	3.03	0.067
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.31	2.71	0.418
Plasma Glucose (mg/dl)	117.34	7.93	< 0.01
HbA1C (Percent)	5.77	0.50	

Table – III: Group Wise Lipid sub-fractional values

Diseased Group (Lipid Profile mg/dl)	Mean	±SD	P value
Serum Cholesterol	187.26	17.46	< 0.01
Serum LDL – C	92.59	11.53	
Serum HDL – C	45.63	4.44	
Serum – TG	169.28	9.83	

DISCUSSION:

In this particular research, we aim to assess the levels of TG and lipid profile among diabetic patients and their interdependence. At present, diabetes is common among the general population and there is an emergent need to investigate various contributing factors of diabetes. Among various prospects, the lipid profile prospect is also important and needs due consideration. Global mortality rate heavily relates with diabetes onset as 400 million global population is at risk of death due to diabetes and the count will increase with every passing year [7]. Diabetes advancement also attributes to the hereditary features. A significant consideration is also required in the field of decisions about the intake of a diet with respect to financial and natural components. Diabetes is avoidable by essential eating regimens [8]. A suitable awareness and adherence to the diet can increase the effectiveness of insulin and glycemic control which will consequently change personal satisfaction generally and quality of life particularly. Diabetes administration is very much difficult in non-

adherence of proper and appropriate dietary intake and it makes the management of diabetes very much difficult [9]. An increased score of HEI refers to partial adherence of the diet intake rules for any single supplement and food accumulation.

A higher score also demonstrates increased use of sufficient segments such as natural products and vegetables. Proposed diet depends on the devouring products useful effects of soil; an expressly stress for the constructive results in order to reduce sort and corpulence of growths. The last three HEI segments incorporate sodium, refined grains and discharge of (calories out of the strong fats, included sugars and liquor). An increased score refers to reduced use [10]. As per the research outcomes, we conclude that a significant and strong association of diabetic retinopathy severity with serum TC, fasting glucose plasma, serum TG, serum LDL-C and serum HDL-C. A strong positive association was also persistent among HbA1c and BSF with serum TC, serum TG, serum LDL-C; while, serum HDL-C had a negatively

weak relation with HbA1c and BSF. HDL-C serum and Smoking reflected a moderate and inverse association with the diabetic retinopathy severity [11]. There was no significant statistical association of diabetic retinopathy with BMI or gender. According to Ahsan, males were 3.5 times more at risk of diabetic retinopathy having increased diabetic duration of 5.46 times and diabetes duration of (≥ 10) years and 1.39 times poor glycemic control with HbA1c ($\geq 7\%$). These factors were significant in the development and progression of retinopathy [12].

CONCLUSION:

As per the research outcomes, we conclude that a significant and strong association of diabetic retinopathy severity with serum TC, fasting glucose plasma, serum TG, serum LDL-C and serum HDL-C. A strong positive association was also persistent among HbA1c and BSF with serum TC, serum TG, serum LDL-C; while, serum HDL-C had a negatively weak relation with HbA1c and BSF. The levels of serum LDL-C, cholesterol and TG were increased; whereas, level of serum HDL-C was reduced among diabetes patients.

REFERENCES:

- Zimmermann GS, Bastos MF, Dias Goncalves TE, Chambrone L, Duarte PM. Local and circulating levels of adipocytokines in obese and normal-weight individuals with chronic periodontitis. *J Periodontol.* 2013 May;84(5):624-33.
- Wheeler ML, Dunbar SA, Jacks LM, Karmally W, Mayer-Davis EJ, Wylie-Rosett J, Yancy WS Jr. Macronutrients, food groups, and eating patterns in the management of diabetes: a systematic review of the literature, 2010. *Diabetes Care.* 2012;35(2):434-445.
- A Jala O, English P, Pinkney J. Systematic review and meta-analysis of different dietary approaches to the management of type 2 diabetes. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 2013;97(3):505-516.
- Newby PK, Tucker KL. Empirically derived eating patterns using factor or cluster analysis: a review. *Nutr Rev.* 2004;62(5):177-203.
- Ocké MC. Evaluation of methodologies for assessing the overall diet: dietary quality scores and dietary pattern analysis. *Proc Nutr Soc.* 2013;72(2):191-199.
- Viana LV, Gross JL, Camargo JL, Zelmanovitz T, da Costa Rocha EP, Azevedo MJ. Prediction of cardiovascular events, diabetic nephropathy, and mortality by albumin concentration in a spot urine sample in patients with type 2 diabetes. *J Diabetes Complications.* 2012;26(5):407-412.
- Cetin EN, Bulgu Y, Ozdemir S, Topsakal S, Akin F, Aybek H, et al. Association of serum lipid levels with diabetic retinopathy. *Int J Ophthalmol.* 2013;6(3):346-349. doi: 10.3980/j.issn.2222-3959.2013.03.17.
- Muluke M, Gold T, Kieffer K, Al-Sahli A, Celenti R, Jiang H, Cremers S, Van Dyke T, Schulze-Spate U. Diet-Induced Obesity and Its Differential Impact on Periodontal Bone Loss. *J Dent Res.* 2016 Feb;95(2):223-9.
- Khader YS, Bawadi HA, Haroun TF, Alomari M, Tayyem RF. The association between periodontal disease and obesity among adults in Jordan. *J Clin Periodontol.* 2009 Jan;36(1):18-24.
- Kiran PU, Srinivas B. Study of glycated haemoglobin, lipid profile and uric acid levels in diabetic retinopathy. *Sch J App Med Sci.* 2015;3(7A):2480-2484.
- Kanski JJ, Bowling B. Retinal Vascular Disease. In: Kanski JJ, editor. *Clinical Ophthalmology – A Systematic Approach.* 7th Ed. London: Elsevier, Saunders; 2011. pp. 533-591.
- Rahman MR, Arslan MI, Hoque MM, Mollah FH, Sherman S. Serum lipids and diabetic retinopathy in newly diagnosed type 2 diabetic subjects. *J Enam Med Coll.* 2011;1(2):63-66.